

Comparison of Growth and Characteristic Properties of Barium Oxalate and Cobalt Oxalate Single Crystals

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Abstract:

The barium oxalate and cobalt oxalate single crystals were grown in agar-agar using gel method. Then compared the growth parameters. The XRD, FTIR, TGA/DTA analysis of the grown crystals confirmed the crystals crystalline. Morphology of the crystals studied from the photography while the structures of the crystals were studied from XRD. Thermal analysis reveals the decomposing temperature of the crystals.

Keywords: Barium oxalate, Crystal growth and Cobalt oxalate.

INTRODUCTION

Crystal growth is the basis of numerous technology improvements. The gel growth method is the most efficient and simple process of crystal growth. It is considered more useful at ambient temperature and has an inexpensive process. The contribution of gel method in crystallization has been significant. This method has been successfully developed as one promising way of growing single crystals and gives many interesting results, from simple metals salts to complex compounds. Single crystals are the backbone of the modern technology of logical revolution [1-3]. The impact of single crystal, is clearly visible in industries like semiconductors, optics etc. Growth and characterization of oxalate single crystals have attracted many researchers single crystals of oxalate single crystal have been grown and reported. Now a day great attention has been devoted on the growth and characterization of oxalate crystal with the aim of identifying new materials for practical purposes. It is well established that there are extensive study on oxalate based crystal grown by gel technique; however, we have found that there are few reports on the barium and cobalt oxalate based crystal because of their chemical properties. Therefore, in the present study, we have investigated the growth mechanism of barium oxalate and cobalt oxalate crystals. All both types of crystals were grown by gel method by using single diffusion techniques [4].

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EXPERIMENTAL

In the present work, barium oxalate and cobalt oxalate single crystals were grown by single diffusion technique. The growth of barium oxalate crystals was carried out in agar-agar gel by adopting the similar technique as reported (Dalal and Saraf 2009) [6]. Barium chloride (BaCl_2 , 99.9%), Cobalt chloride (CoCl_2 , 99.9%) Oxalic acid ($\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, 99%), Agar-Agar powder ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_9$) were used as the starting materials. All chemicals were AR grade. The borosilicate glass tube was used as crystallization apparatus. The glass tubes used for single diffusion were of 25cm length and 2.5cm outer diameter. The solution of different (0.5, 1.0, 1.2, 1.5, 2M) were prepared and store in clean glassware. Agar-Agar gel was prepared by mixing (0.5 to 2.0gm) of agar powder in 100ml double distilled water at boiling temperature. Barium chloride and Cobalt chloride of concentration 0.5 to 2 M and oxalic acid of concentration 0.5 to 2M were used as reactants [5]. The prepared solution of oxalic acid were then transfer into the test tube, after that appropriate volume of agar gel poured in this test tube and the mouth of test tube closed by the cotton plug and then kept undisturbed for aging period of few days. Usually with 24 to 36 hours the gel was found to set which depends on the environmental temperature. Room temperature and atmospheric effect also plays an important role on gelation, aging that is evaporation of water molecules from on surface of gel. It was observed that the mixture in glass tube was initially transparent and slowly turn milky white. After insuring firm gel setting it was kept for aging for 2 to 3 days. Aging makes the gel harder and reduces the diameter of capillaries present in the gel. After setting and aging over the set gel solution of second reactant (supernatants) of desire volume and molarity was poured gently along the wall and allowed to diffuse into the gel medium. The open end of test tube was closed with cotton plug to prevent evaporation and contamination of the exposed surface by dust particles and impurities of atmosphere and was kept undisturbed [6].The following chemical reactions were employed for the growth

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig.1 a) shows Liesegang rings and the grown crystals, b) shows working reaction during crystal growth in test tube. c) shows Harvested crystals of cobalt oxalate and d) barium oxalate single crystals

Figure 1 a)

Figure 1 b)

Figure 2 c)

Figure 1 d)

The characterization of the pure and doped crystals were carried using XRD, FTIR, thermal analysis, UV absorption spectrum and scanning electron micrographs and their characteristics are compared.

X-Ray diffraction: The X-ray diffraction pattern of barium oxalate and cobalt oxalate crystals are shown in Fig. 2. The patterns of these two samples were taken at room temperature in order to study the structure of the materials. Both materials were found to be single crystalline. From the XRD pattern it is noticed that the peaks obtained at 23.83, 29.44, 39.37, 44.79, 46.71, and 59.02⁰ are corresponds to the (002), (102), (301), (020), (120) and (-104) lattice planes of the barium oxalate crystals and for the cobalt oxalate the peaks are observed at 18.75, 30.23, 34.96, 43.28, 51.19, 56.09 and 60.73⁰ are corresponding to the (111), (220), (311), (021), (314), (422) and (511) lattice planes [3]. The lattice parameters of barium oxalate $a = 8.2425 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 4.0457 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.4707 \text{ \AA}$, volume of unit cell, $V = 215.61 \text{ \AA}^3$ and of cobalt oxalate $a = 5.39820 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.03100 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.73590 \text{ \AA}$, volume of unit cell, $V = 155.77 \text{ \AA}^3$. From the calculated (hkl) and 'd' values, it is found that the both oxalate crystals crystallize in the monoclinic system. Table 1. Comparison of Lattice parameters.

FTIR: Thermo- Nicolet, Avatar 370 spectrophotometer is used for the study of FTIR spectrum of both samples. KBr is used as the beam splitter and also as detector. The peaks are identified in comparison with earlier reports. The broad peak at 3600-3400 cm⁻¹ due to anti symmetric O-H stretching suggest the presence of water of crystallization in both crystals. All the functional groups are observed in both types of crystals and obtained data is summarized in Table 2 [7].

Table 1. Comparison of Lattice parameters

Material	Chemical formula	System	Lattice parameters a, b, c, α, β, γ	Volume (Å) ³
Barium Oxalate	BaC ₂ O ₄	Monoclinic	a = 8.2425 Å b = 4.0457 Å c = 6.4707 Å	215.61 Å ³
Cobalt Oxalate	CoC ₂ O ₄	Monoclinic	a = 5.39820 Å b = 5.03100 Å c = 5.73590 Å	155.77 Å ³

Table 2 Summary of vibrational infrared frequencies of different bonds found in the grown crystals

Fundamental frequencies	Barium oxalate	Cobalt oxalate
O-H Stretching and water of crystallization	3566	3366
Metal oxygen bonding	590	487
C = O stretching	51652	1621

Fig. 2 X-ray diffraction pattern of a) Cobalt oxalate b) barium Oxalate

Fig. 3 TGA of Barium oxalate and cobalt oxalate crystal grown by agar-agar gel

From the TG diagram, barium oxalate crystal showed four stages of weight loss. Thus the curve shows a gradual mass loss. From this graph, the weight loss starts at around 50°C and steps at

172°C in which weight loss of 5.17%. It is observed that the material is stable up to 50°C. The second stage of decomposition is from 172°C to 277°C in which weight loss of 25.68%. In the third stage of decomposition is from 277°C to 435°C in which weight loss of 36.68%. In last stage of decomposition is from 435°C to 478°C in which weight loss 13.45%. The residue at the end is at 478°C. The TG thermo gram cobalt oxalate reveals that decomposition starts at 30°C and steps at 177°C in which weight loss 17.46%. In the second stage of decomposition in the temperature range 200°C to 247°C, the total weight loss 3.411%. In the third stage of decomposition total weight loss 36.88% was observed in the temperature range 247°C to 260°C and last stage in the temperature range 892°C to 930°C total weight loss of 2.538% was obtained. The residue at the end is at 930°C. [8-11]

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